

Noise Network Plus: A New Interdisciplinary Network to Address the Grand Challenges of Noise Pollution

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Overview

Noise Network Plus is a new interdisciplinary network designed to address the grand challenges for noise pollution for the next 10-15 years, supported by the UK Engineering and Physical Science Research Council (EPSRC).

Importance of Noise

- Noise pollution has major impact on health, society, wildlife (second only to air pollution)
- Human Health: causes stress, leads to sleep disturbance, heart disease
 - England: 40% adults exposed to harmful levels of noise (roads etc) Health cost est. £7-10b
 - Social aspects: poorest in society, already have poorer health
 - Diversity: not everyone responds in the same way e.g., more impact on elderly, children, people with autism
- Wildlife: problems for communication, stress, fertility, migration
- Noise pollution is increasing: growth in cities, transport, shipping
- Recognised as important health issue by WHO, UK Government, EU, ...

Noise as a Tomorrow's Engineering Research Challenge

- EPSRC Tomorrow's Engineering Research Challenges (TERC) report aimed to Identify the **most important challenges** that face engineers over the **next 10-15 years**

Tomorrow's Engineering Research Challenges (TERC) - Overview

Noise Network Plus: Vision

- Mission-oriented inter-organisational research & innovation network
- Addressing noise as a “wicked problem”
- Improve health & wellbeing, wildlife & sustainability, AI systems & sensors
- Build out from UK Acoustics Network Plus (UKAN+)
- Create new multi- & inter-disciplinary community
- Support from: Industry, Professional Engineering Institutions, Charities & 3rd Sector, Government & Policy Organizations, ... (60+ partners)

Objectives

- Create new **inter-organisational network** to address challenge of noise
- Undertake **public engagement & outreach**, involve wide community
- Bring community together to co-design a set of **noise-related Missions**
- Fund **explorative pilot projects** in noise
- Develop **full-scale**, high-quality Mission-inspired **research funding bids**
- Reimagine **engineering training & education**, to include **noise, systems thinking**
- **Embed Network activities** across organisations to ensure **continuation**

Launch Meeting – London/Hybrid, 18 March 2025

- Over 100 delegates from industry, universities, charities, government, ...

Planned Network Activities

New inter-organisational network - Universities, industry, charities, govt, ...

- Workshops (hybrid), “world cafés”, secondments/exchanges, ...
- EDI - promote, monitor and report diversity

Public engagement and outreach – Engage from the start

- Public & policy interest - contribute to co-design of Missions
- Artists in residence, podcast (“The Rest is Just Noise”), competitions

Mission-oriented approach - Co-design of long-term “Missions”

- Example: “Halve societal cost of transport noise by 2040”
- Translate into Funded projects, Roadmaps - Embed to continue beyond Network

Pilot Projects – Explorative, cross-disciplinary, cross-sector

- Competitive calls, addressing TERC-related priorities & identified Missions
- Applicant support via Collaboration Workshops

Large-scale research funding bids - Inspired by Missions

- Grant-writing retreats - Peer support for collaborative bid development
- Impact workshops - Showcase research to industry, policymakers, charities, etc.

Education, training and skills

- Early-career: e.g. Summer Schools
- Noise in undergraduate Engineering
- Work with Centres for Doctoral Training
- Next Generation: Schools & young people

Embed activities across organisations

- Build connections to universities, industry, policymakers, institutions, charities, ...
- Organise joint “silo-breaking” multi-organization webinars & workshops
- Build long-lasting inter-organisation connections to outlive 3-year Network

Building a healthier society and environment - “engineering a quieter future”

For more information – subscribe at <https://www.jiscmail.ac.uk/noise>

Partners

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| Aecom | Clarke Saunders Acoustics | Matelys - Research Lab | Saab UK Ltd |
| Alan Turing Institute (DTNet+) | Computational Audiology Network | Mayer Brown Ltd. | Sonos, Inc. |
| Amey Limited | Engineering Professors' Council | Microflow Technologies | Stantec UK Ltd |
| Apex Acoustics | Environment Agency | Mott MacDonald Ltd | Strategic Aviation Special Interest Group (SASIG) |
| Association of Noise Consultants | Farrat Isolevel Ltd | National Highways | Temple Group |
| Atlas Elektronik | Forest Research | National Physical Laboratory | Thales UK Limited |
| Audio Engineering Society UK Section | Ghent University | Noise Abatement Society | Timbral Ltd. |
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| AWE plc | HEAD Acoustics | Offshore Renewable Energy | UK Hearing Conservation Association |
| Bat Conservation Trust | Health and Safety Executive | Catapult | University of Derby |
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